

A Study on the Privileges of Online Consumers

by Abinashi Tirkey, B.Ed.,

Department of Commerce,

Tagore College of Education, Port Blair - 744101

&

Deepshikha Biswas, Resource Person,

Department of Commerce,

M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204

Introduction :

Online shopping is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly buy goods or services from a seller over the Internet using a web browser or a mobile app. Consumerism seeks to inform and protect consumers by insisting on practices like honest packaging and advertising, product guarantees and improved safety standards. It is a movement that sets policies to regulate the products, services, methods and standards of manufacturers, sellers and advertisers in the interest of buyers. Modern economy is consumer oriented. Every action revolves around him. The present paper highlights the privileges of online consumers. Since 1994, the Internet has grown more quickly than any other medium in history. Nearly 1 billion people are currently online worldwide. However, there are still 5 billion people that are not. This chapter will examine reasons for such a high rate on non-online citizens and how e-marketers are adjusting to the fact that the percentage of citizens online may never exceed 25%.

Consumers Buying Behavior in Digital Environment :

The marketing around the digital environment, customer's buying behaviour may not be influenced and controlled by the brand and firm, when they make a

buying decision that might concern the interactions with search engine, recommendations, online reviews and other information. With the quickly separate of the digital devices environment, people are more likely to use their mobile phones, computers, tablets and other digital devices to gather information. In other words, the digital environment has a growing effect on consumer's mind and buying behaviour. In an online shopping environment, interactive decision may have an influence on aid customer decision making. Each customer is becoming more interactive, and though online reviews customers can influence other potential buyers' behaviors. In addition, not only those reviews, people morerely on other people's post information about product commends on social media. There will shows common problems in the past and some solutions or comments of the merchants will be attached for customer reference.

Subsequently, risk and trust would also are two important factors affecting people's' behavior in digital environments. Customer considers switching between e-channels, because they are mainly influence by the comparison with offline shopping, involving growth of security, financial and performance-risks. In other words, a customer shopping online that they may receive more risk than people shopping in stores. There are three factors may influence people to do the buying decision, firstly, people cannot examine whether the product satisfy their needs and wants before they receive it. Secondly, customer may concern at after-sale services. Finally, customer may afraid that they cannot fully understand the language used in e-sales. Based on those factors customer perceive risk may as a significantly reason influence the online purchasing behaviour.

Online retailers has place much emphasis on customer trust aspect, trust is another way driving customer's behaviour in digital environment, which can depend on customer's attitude and expectation. Indeed, the company's products design or ideas cannot meet customer's expectations. Customer's purchase intention based on rational expectations, and additionally impacts on emotional trust. Moreover, those expectations can be also establish on the product information and revision from others.

Benefits of Online Shopping :

Online shopping is becoming increasingly popular for a variety of reasons:

- Saves time and efforts.
- The convenience of shopping at home.
- Wide variety /range of products is available.
- Good discounts /lower prices.
- Get detailed information about the product.
- We can compare various models /brands.

Using Express Shipping Options when Shopping Online :

One of the distinct advantages of online shopping is the shipping methods which are available. These options are especially beneficial to online shoppers who are guilty of often waiting until the last minute to purchase items as gifts or items that are necessary for other reasons. For these online shoppers express shipping is one of the most beneficial features. Although the shopper will pay significantly more for express shipping options the shopper will have the advantage of being able to purchase an item the day before it is necessary and have the item delivered directly to the necessary party.

Kiosks :

Kiosks are used to offer information, provide Internet access, and allow customers to shop online. Web kiosks enable retailers: to bring the Internet into their stores. While in the store, customers can shop online at the kiosk at the store's Web site. In-store kiosks can help sell a retailer's Web site and direct traffic there. Kiosks can also be a way to introduce non-Internet users to the Internet and encourage them to do more online shopping. Kiosks are also a cost-effective way to increase the number of products available. They help retailers capture sales that might have been lost due to out-of-stock merchandise. If kiosks became widely accepted by consumers, retailers would be free to build smaller stores and let the kiosks provide access to a wider range of products.

Conclusion :

Web based shopping is becoming more popular now a day with the increase in the usage of World Wide Web. Understanding customer's need for online shop-

ping has become challenge for marketers. Specially understanding the consumer's attitudes towards online shopping, making improvement in the factors that influence consumers to shop online and working on factors that affect consumers to shop online will help marketers to gain the competitive edge over others.

References :

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